

Exploring the Therapeutics of Laser in Oral Medicine: A Review

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Abstract

Since the 1990s, lasers have revolutionized dentistry, especially for managing oral mucosal lesions. They provide precise diagnosis and minimally invasive treatment, reducing bleeding and speeding up healing. Lasers are also used for biopsies and in palliative care to promote tissue regeneration and reduce pain. Additionally, they complement traditional treatments like chemotherapy, helping target residual tumour cells and aiding recovery. Overall, lasers improve patient outcomes and comfort, playing a crucial role in modern dental practices.

Introduction

In 1960, Theodore Maiman created the first operational laser, a groundbreaking device that emitted a red light beam from a ruby crystal. This invention marked a significant milestone in the field of physics and soon caught the attention of researchers in various fields, including dentistry. The ability of lasers to precisely focus energy onto a small area without causing extensive damage to surrounding tissues made them an attractive option for medical and dental applications. By 1965, Dr. Leon Goldman, often referred to as the "Father of Laser Dentistry," conducted pioneering experiments using the ruby laser on tooth enamel. His early work demonstrated that lasers could affect dental hard tissues, sparking further interest and research into their potential uses in dentistry.¹

Throughout the 1970s and 1980s, extensive studies were conducted to explore different types of Lasers, such as the CO₂ and Nd:YAG Lasers, and their interactions with various dental tissues. Researchers focused on understanding how these lasers could be used for both hard and soft tissue procedures, identifying the optimal parameters for cutting, coagulating, and vaporizing tissues while minimizing thermal damage. The CO₂ laser, with its wavelength in the infrared spectrum, proved particularly effective for soft tissue applications, such as removing oral lesions and performing periodontal surgeries. It allowed for precise cutting with minimal bleeding due to its ability to coagulate blood vessels effectively. The Nd:YAG

Laser, with a longer wavelength, showed promise in both soft and hard tissue applications, including caries removal and cavity preparation.

By the mid-1970s, lasers had been integrated into clinical practice for soft tissue procedures in dentistry. CO₂ Lasers, in particular, were widely adopted for their ability to efficiently treat oral lesions, perform frenectomies, and manage periodontal conditions. These Lasers offered several advantages over traditional surgical techniques, including reduced postoperative pain, faster healing times, and improved patient comfort. The ability to achieve precise cuts with minimal thermal damage to surrounding tissues was a significant breakthrough, leading to better outcomes for patients and increased acceptance among dental professionals.¹

The fundamental principles behind Lasers, encapsulated in the acronym Laser - "Light amplification by stimulated emission of radiation" - are rooted in Albert Einstein's 1917 theory of stimulated emission. This theory describes how electrons in an excited state can be stimulated to emit light of a specific wavelength, resulting in the amplification of that light. The development of the laser was a culmination of decades of theoretical and experimental work in physics, and its adaptation to medical and

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dental applications was a natural progression, given its unique properties.

Despite often being perceived as a new technology in the dental field, lasers have a rich history dating back over six decades. Their application in dentistry has evolved significantly since the early experiments in the 1960s. Today, lasers are commonly used in various dental specialties, including periodontics, endodontics, oral surgery, and pediatric dentistry. They are employed for procedures such as cavity preparation, soft tissue management, periodontal therapy, and even in the treatment of sleep apnea. The versatility of lasers, combined with their ability to reduce the invasiveness of procedures and enhance patient comfort, has made them an invaluable tool in modern dental practice.²

This article aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the history of laser technology, the mechanisms of laser-tissue interaction, the various wavelengths used in dental procedures, and the wide range of clinical applications. Understanding these aspects will enable clinicians to make informed decisions about incorporating laser technology into their practices, ensuring optimal patient care and expanding the range of treatment options available. By mastering the use of lasers, dental professionals can enhance their ability to perform precise, minimally invasive procedures, ultimately improving patient outcomes and satisfaction.

History

The Laser, or “Light Amplification by Stimulated Emission of Radiation,” has transformed various fields since its inception. Initially derived from Maser technology, Laser development is rooted in significant scientific breakthroughs. Albert Einstein laid the theoretical foundation for stimulated emission in 1917, which eventually led to the development of LASER technology.³ In 1964, Charles Townes, Nikolay Basov, and Aleksandr Prokhorov received the Nobel Prize for their pioneering work in this field.

The term “LASER” was introduced in 1959 by Gordon Gould, and the first functional Laser was built by Theodore Maiman in 1960.⁴ This was followed by innovations such as the ruby LASER, Nd:YAG Laser, and the Argon Laser in the early 1960s.⁵ The ruby LASER was the first to be used medically, particularly for retinal treatments, but it was found unsuitable for dental applications due to high thermal effects. The CO₂ Laser, developed in 1964 by Kumar Patel, significantly advanced dental procedures with its effective interaction with enamel.

Today, Laser technology is widely used in medicine, dentistry, communications, and manufacturing, highlighting the interdisciplinary collaboration and impact of theoretical physics on practical applications.⁶

Classification

Lasers in dental practice are classified based on their medium, tissue applicability, wavelength range, and associated risks.⁷

1. Soft Tissue Lasers: These include KTP, Diode, and Nd:YAG Lasers, which are absorbed by pigments in soft tissues and pathogens like *Porphyromonas gingivalis* and other inflammatory tissues. CO₂ Lasers interact with free water molecules in soft tissue and can vaporize the intra-

cellular water of pathogens.

2. Soft and Hard Tissue Lasers: Erbium lasers, such as Er, Cr:YSGG, and Er:YAG, are versatile “all-tissue” instruments due to their high absorption in both hydroxyapatite crystals and water in soft and hard tissues. However, they have limited hemostatic ability because they are not absorbed by hemoglobin and have specific pulse durations.⁷

Mechanism of Action

Laser-Tissue Interactions in Dentistry

In dentistry, lasers interact with tissues through transmission, reflection, scattering, and absorption:

- 1. Transmission:** The laser beam passes through a medium without significant interaction. Some lasers, like diode and Nd:YAG, can pass through water and eye components but are absorbed by the retina.⁸
- 2. Reflection:** The laser beam bounces off a surface, which can direct energy to unintended areas, posing safety risks.⁸
- 3. Scatter:** The laser beam spreads out after interacting with a medium, potentially causing unwanted heat and tissue damage but can be useful in some applications, like curing resins.
- 4. Absorption:** The laser energy is absorbed by the tissue and converted into heat, allowing precise cutting or removal of tissue. Absorption depends on factors like tissue type and laser wavelength.⁹

Figure -Possible Laser Light- Tissue Interaction

Photo Biological Effects On Tissues

- Infrared Light is absorbed by water.
- Visible and Ultraviolet Light are absorbed by hemoglobin and melanin.
- Violet and Ultraviolet Light have limited penetration due to absorption by proteins.⁹

Figure – A portion of the Electromagnetic Spectrum showing Dental Laser Wavelengths being used for Treatment

Five Interaction Mechanisms of Lasers in Biomedicine

- 1. Optical Effects:** Used for diagnostics like cancer screening and high-resolution imaging by creating optical signals with laser light.
- 2. Photomechanical Effects:** Applied in laser lithotripsy and tattoo removal, where laser energy creates acoustic waves to disrupt tissues.
- 3. Photochemical Effects:** Used in photodynamic therapy and resin polymerization, where laser energy triggers chemical reactions or breaks bonds.⁸
- 4. Photothermal Effects:** Applied in resurfacing and surgical procedures, where laser energy is converted to heat for precise cutting and hemostasis.^{8,9}
- 5. Photobiostimulative Effects:** Includes low-level laser therapy and acne treatment, stimulating cellular activity to promote healing and reduce inflammation.⁹

Factors Determining Laser Suitability

The suitability of a laser for various dental procedures is influenced by:

- **Wavelength:** Determines how the laser interacts with different tissues.
- **Energy Fluence:** The energy delivered per unit area affects the treatment outcome.
- **Optical Characteristics of Tissues:** How tissues absorb, reflect, scatter, or transmit laser light.
- **Laser Operation Mode:** Continuous mode delivers constant energy, while pulsed modes allow for tailored effects.
- **Ultraviolet Lasers (100-381 nm):** Ionize tissues through photochemical desorption.
- **Infrared Lasers (700-10,000 nm):** Cause significant heating, leading to protein denaturation, tissue decomposition, and charring.

Soft Tissue	Hard Tissue
Cut, coagulate, ablate or vaporize	Faster ablation
Dry surgical field	Reduced peri-operative cracking
Reduced post-operative edema	scope for minimally invasive restorative treatment of early caries
Sterilization of tissue	Reduced pulpal temperature rise
Decreased amount of scarring	Cavity sterilization

Table: Benefits of laser tissue interaction

Laser Energy And Tissue Temperature

When a laser is absorbed by tissue, it raises the temperature and produces various effects based on tissue water content.¹⁰

- Hyperthermia: Initial temperature rise above normal, not destructive.
- 50°C: Deactivates non-sporulating bacteria.
- 60°C: Causes protein denaturation and coagulation without vaporization.
- 70-80°C: Tissue welding or anastomosis, where collagen molecules bind together.
- 100°C: Ablation, where water vaporizes, removing Tissue layers.
- Above 200°C: Carbonization, where tissue dehydrates and burns, an undesirable effect.

Laser absorption depends on chromophores:

- Soft Tissues: Water, melanin, and hemoglobin.
- Hard Tissues: Water and hydroxyapatite.¹⁰

Laser Application In Dentistry¹¹

Application	Possible laser types
Basic research Laser tissue interaction	All types
Oral medicine Laser doppler flow metre Laser induced fluorescence (caries diagnosis)	He Ne, diodes He Ne, diodes Diode
Photodynamic therapy (for treatment of oral cancer) To release fibrotic bands in OSMF Oral soft tissue lesions, frictional keratosis, leukoplakia, verrucous carcinoma)	Er Cr:YSGG Diode
Conservative dentistry DH Cavity preparation Composite resin light curing Tooth surface conditioning, removal of defective composite restoration	Co2, Nd:YAG, Ec. YAG, Diode CO2, Nd:YAG, Er:YAG Argon, Er:YAG
Endodontics Root canal treatment, apicoectomy	Nd:YAG, CO2 Co2, Nd:YAG
Periodontics Laser-assisted curettage Gingivectomy and gingivoplasty	Nd:YAG, diode CO2
Analgesic effect and bio-stimulation Stimulation of wound healing	He Ne, diodes, Nd:YAG

Table: Laser Applications in Dentistry

Diode Laser

Diode lasers, made from semiconductor crystals, emit wavelengths from 800 nm to 980 nm in the near-infrared spectrum. They are used in continuous or pulsed modes for soft tissue surgery and deeper coagulation¹². Diode lasers are absorbed well by pigmented tissues but are less effective on tooth structure, making them ideal for procedures close to teeth.¹³ Proper cooling and fiber preparation are essential to avoid overheating and ensure effective cutting. They are also used in diagnostic tools like the Diodent, which detects carious tooth structure through fluorescence, and in low-level laser therapy (LLLT) for non-surgical bio stimulation.¹⁴

Laser Delivery Systems, Emission Modes

Effective laser energy delivery requires precise systems like KTP, diode, and Nd:YAG lasers with flexible fibre-optic setups.¹⁵ Diode lasers have a rectangular beam profile with high divergence on one axis and low on the other. For dental procedures, maintaining contact with the tissue using fluid helps reduce energy loss¹⁶. Protective measures such as laser barriers and disposable parts are important. The fibre tip's focal point delivers maximum energy, with defocusing increasing coverage for haemostasis. Lasers can operate in continuous wave or pulsed modes, offering adjustable pulse durations for varied effects.¹⁶

Figure Modes of Application¹⁵

Application of Diode Laser

Portable and cost-effective lasers are becoming the preferred choice for treating oral mucosal lesions and other dental conditions. For high-grade premalignant diseases like oral leukoplakia, excision or laser ablation remains the gold standard. Moderate and low-grade pre-malignancies may be managed with observation or ablation.¹⁷

- **Fibromas:** Treated with diode lasers (975 nm, 5W, continuous wave) for soft tissue surgery.
- **Mucocele:** Unroofed and excised using diode lasers (975 nm, 5W, continuous wave); re-epithelization takes about three weeks.
- **Palatal Lesions:** Traumatic fibromas in the soft palate are treated with diode lasers (975 nm, continuous wave).
- **Epulis Fissuratum:** Removed with diode lasers combining fibroma removal (975 nm, 5W, continuous wave) and gingivectomy modes (975 nm, 3W, 10 ms).
- **Impacted Teeth:** Exposure of soft tissue impactions is

performed with diode lasers (975 nm, 3W, continuous wave).

- **Dental Implantology:** Diode lasers assist in uncovering implants, with care to avoid heat conduction.¹²
- **Caries and Calculus Detection:** Diodent, a diode laser at 655 nm, detects caries and subgingival calculus.¹⁸
- **Loose Soft-Tissue Surgery:** Includes frenectomies, hemangiomas, mucoceles, and treatment of nonerosive lichen planus and herpes lesions.
- **Fixed Soft-Tissue Surgery:** Diode lasers (810 nm) are used for gingival hyperplasia, tooth exposure, and hyperpigmentation.
- **Periodontal Therapy:** Diode lasers (810 nm) remove diseased pocket lining and disinfect periodontal pockets (0.8-1W).¹³
- **Endodontics:** Diode lasers (810 nm) aid in root canal disinfection and debris removal, though slightly less effective than Nd:YAG lasers.⁹
- **Tooth Whitening:** Diodes (810-980 nm) are used for photothermal bleaching, with power settings of 2W to activate bleaching agents.¹⁷
- **Low-Level Laser Therapy (LLLT):** Uses diode lasers for non-destructive biostimulation, enhancing fibroblast production, collagen synthesis, and pain relief. LLLT benefits include treating hypertrophic lesions, operculectomy, gingival contouring, and periodontal surgeries.¹⁰

Advantages of Diode Laser

1. Sterilization: Reduces bacteria and pathogens, ensuring a sterile field.⁷
2. Less Edema and Scarring: Seals lymphatic vessels, minimizing swelling and scarring.¹⁶
3. Hemostasis: Provides excellent bleeding control, reducing the need for sutures.^{7,8}
4. Blended Healing: Seamlessly integrates with surrounding tissues.
5. Better Visualization: Improved bleeding control enhances visibility and reduces infection risk.
6. Versatile Use: Safe for various patient groups, including children and the elderly.
7. Reduced Anxiety: Lowers patient anxiety about surgical procedures.⁸

Disadvantages of Diode Laser

1. High Cost and Training: Expensive and requires specialized training.⁸
2. Technique Changes: Requires adaptation from traditional dental instruments.
3. Accessibility Issues: Risk of overheating and air embolism.
4. Wavelength Specificity: No single wavelength suits all procedures.¹³
5. Eye Safety: Hazardous to eyesight.⁸

Laser Safety

According to ANSI and OSHA, lasers are categorized into four basic types based on safety standards.¹⁹

1. **Warning Signs:** Display laser warning symbols outside the clinic.
2. **Eye Protection:** Use protective eyewear for everyone to prevent eye damage from direct or reflected laser light.

- 3. Tissue Protection:** Take care to avoid injury to adjacent tissues and dental structures.
- 4. Regular Maintenance:** Ensure equipment is regularly serviced and checked for safety.⁸

Class	Description
I	Low-powered lasers that are safe to use.
IIa	Low powered visible laser that are hazardous only when viewed directly for longer than 1000 seconds (15 min approximately).
IIb	Low-powered visible lasers that are hazardous only when viewed directly for longer than 0.25 seconds.
IIIa	Medium-powered lasers that are normally hazardous if viewed for less than 0.25 seconds without magnifying optics
IIIb	Medium-powered lasers that can be hazardous if viewed directly
IV	High powered lasers (>0.25W) that produce ocular, skin and fire hazards.

Table: Types Of Lasers²²

Management of Oral Recurrent Aphthous Ulcers and Lasers

Low-Level Laser Therapy (LLLT) for Recurrent Aphthous Stomatitis (RAS)

LLLT delivers non-destructive energy to target tissues, either alongside or independently from high-level laser treatments. It enhances cell metabolism, tissue regeneration, and reduces pain and inflammation, accelerating healing. LLLT is effective in treating Recurrent Aphthous Stomatitis (RAS).¹⁰

1. Prasad & Pai (2013)¹⁸: Found that CO₂ laser therapy provided immediate pain relief and faster healing in minor aphthous ulcers compared to a placebo.
2. Misra et al. (2013)²⁰: Reported that laser therapy significantly reduced burning sensation in a patient with aphthous ulcers.
3. Kaur et al. (2017)²³: Concluded that diode laser treatment for soft tissue lesions was less painful and provided easy ablation and decontamination compared to conventional methods.

Triamcinolone Acetonide

Introduced in the 1940s, glucocorticoids like triamcinolone acetonide are widely used for their potent anti-inflammatory effects. They work by suppressing immune cell activity and reducing inflammatory mediators. Triamcinolone acetonide, often applied topically, is effective for severe aphthous ulcers and oral inflammatory conditions. Studies comparing it to other treatments, such as chlorhexidine and tacrolimus, show it to be highly effective with similar outcomes to other agents. Triamcinolone acetonide's efficacy in managing oral

inflammation is attributed to its local anti-inflammatory properties and minimal systemic absorption when used in topical formulations.²¹

Conclusion

In conclusion, lasers have transformed oral medicine by enhancing the diagnosis and treatment of various conditions with precision and minimal invasiveness. Their versatility spans a wide range of applications, including soft and hard tissue surgeries, periodontal therapy, caries detection, tooth whitening, and low-level laser therapy (LLLT) for pain relief and tissue regeneration. The ability to finely control laser parameters ensures targeted treatment while minimizing damage to surrounding tissues. Understanding Laser-Tissue interactions and adhering to safety protocols are crucial for optimizing outcomes and preventing accidents. Research has demonstrated that lasers can offer immediate pain relief and accelerated healing for conditions like recurrent aphthous ulcers, often outperforming traditional treatments such as corticosteroids. However, high costs and the need for specialized training remain challenges. Future advancements in laser technology are expected to enhance accessibility and effectiveness, solidifying lasers as a valuable tool in modern dentistry and improving patient care and comfort.

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